

Article

Colonial Bengal, Muslim Women and the Edges of Social Change

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Abstract

In this paper the author has explained how social change occurred among Muslim women in colonial Bengal through a historical analysis.

Key terms: colonial Bengal, historiography, life-world, Muslim women

Introduction

Developments in colonial Bengal since the 19th century have produced serious repercussions on the future definition of the nation and the evolving frames of society that the nation is yet to consistently deal with in its post-colonial time. Any reflection from a critical standpoint would suggest that the developments in the 19th century Bengal need to be unfolded in the light of various moves and contradictions. Apart from the issues like the formation of national identity and the problematic of dignified citizenship in a subject nation we also come

across the impact of those developments on gender relations. All those were under the close surveillance of the colonial rulers as well as the votaries of the civilizing mission of the British rule and the antagonists of the British rule (G. Forbes, p.13). Therefore, for various critical issues that have been drawn into the biography of the post-colonial nation we need to look back to the developments in Bengal during the 19th century.

The main objective of this paper is not to delve into the details of the main currents of historiography on the splendour of the 19th century Bengal renaissance and various facets of its magnificence. But, there is no denying the fact that any discussion on the 19th century renaissance cannot exclude a judgement of the discernible components like enlightenment, rationalism and egalitarianism. All these variables gave birth to a broad normative frame, refined by individualism, self-reliance and liberal-rational outlook against the grip of backwardness and orthodoxy. Hence, we need to devote a fresh thinking to explore whether the aura of that new awakening could articulate an authentic call for 'egalitarianism' and 'emancipation' of the colonized Indians from distresses of subjection during the colonial period.

From one standpoint it is argued that the splendour of enlightenment had stimulated anti-colonial nationalism to ride on the urge for denouncing obscurantism, orthodoxy and iniquitous social structure. In the words of K. N. Panikkar, "The cultural-ideological struggle in colonial India had two mutually complementary facets. The first was directed against the backward elements of tradition, culture and ideology and was expressed in the reformation and regeneration of socio-religious institutions. The second was an attempt to contend with colonial culture and ideology. According to him it was an awareness of the inadequacies of traditional institutions to cope with the new situation created by colonial intrusion (Panikkar, 1986)

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19th century Bengal

19th century Bengal is characterized by the arrival of intelligentsia and radicals like Rammohun Ray, Derozio, Bankimchandra, Vidyasagar, Keshab Chandra Sen, Shibnath Shastri, Rabindra Nath Tagore and so on. Their pledge for social reform, rational thinking and call for national awakening had an everlasting effect on the minds of the Bengalis whose worldview was on the throes of change due to sustained contact with Western education, Western knowledge-systems and culture. So, it is claimed that the untiring efforts of the luminaries had resurrected the subject nation from despair and stagnation. Nevertheless, there are doubts about the stretch of that new awakening particularly when the directions of changes are explained from the standpoint of marginalized groups and communities and their responses to the elite-based nationalist movement and colonial regime.

It is found that the developments in 19th century Bengal is marked by both splendour and skepticism, although generally the history of making of a new society, new politics and the ensuing culture as we trace in that period is generally explained in the light of the grand narrative called, 'Bengal Renaissance'. From a different standpoint the period is marked by two divergent processes of mass responses: first, the formation of the mainstream Bengali socio-political awakening, which was explicit and dominant; and secondly, some reflexive moves from the discursive world of the underprivileged social groups and communities. The objective of the moves was to explore a space in the emerging landscape of citizenship in Bengal, the epicentre of nationalist politics in the 19th century.

Here, the paper does not attempt a thorough probe into the dichotomy between the dominant and subordinate (subaltern) groups and its effect on the consolidation of anti-colonial nationalism. But, at the same time we cannot

avoid looking at the developments in the 19th century in the light of multi-positioning of the social groups. An account of social and political developments of that period reveals that outside the realm of mainstream anti-colonial movement, undercurrents of change had also begun to take place among the groups. As a result, the fissures growing within the society sustained to throw a considerable impact on the course of anti-British movements and subsequent formation of Indian nationhood and its destiny under colonialism. It may be worthwhile to derive from the subaltern historiography that the inability of the dominating national elites to build up organic links with the entire society was characterized by an amalgam of their loyalty and opposition to foreign rule, a combination in which their scramble for power and privilege prevailed over national considerations. Their failure to identify with the mind of the subaltern groups had paved the way for the autonomous domain of the subaltern movements and consciousness.²

Objective of the study

In backdrop of these underpinnings we now come to the point of exploring the life world of Muslim women in reference to the circumstances in 19th century Bengal. In this inquiry we look into the structural determinants by keeping in mind that Muslim women's life-world was seized within the loop of community's decline and backwardness and molecular changes

² Sen Ashok (1987): *Subaltern Studies, Capital, Class and Community, Subaltern Studies, Vol. V*, p.207

at the end of the 19th century. Their backwardness did not happen all on a sudden, rather had resulted from certain disconcerting developments during the colonial period which precipitated their decline. Viewed from this standpoint, the discussion looks into major developments, such as: i. abolition of Persian as the language of colonial administration and antipathy to English education; ii. Ashraf-Atraf dichotomy among the Muslims; iii. Urdu-Bengali contradiction; iv. Muslim response to nationalist politics and Hindu-Muslim relations; v. construction of domestic ideology, based on orthodoxy; and vi. private life and the dynamics of change leading to subtle changes in shaping the life-world of Muslim women in a different way during the 19th century.

Abolition of Persian

One key factor that contributed to the decline of Muslim domination in colonial society and administration was the replacement of Persian by English as the language of colonial administration. It caused a major shift within the structure of power that eroded the social and political base of the Muslims who could not adapt to the emergence of new power relations under colonialism. Persian was used in the courts and state-administration in pre-British India and also during the British rule till its annulment in 1837. Muslim elites and nobles rose to prominence under the patronage of the Muslim rulers. But its abolition in 1837 and their perennial antipathy to Western education had robbed them of the opportunity to accommodate with the successive changes towards Anglicization of the colonized society to strengthen the British rule, which was in tune with T. B. Macaulay's famous saying in 1835: "... it is impossible for us, with our limited means, to attempt to educate the body of the people. We must at present do our best to form a class who may be interpreters between us and the millions whom we govern; a class of persons, Indian in blood and colour, but English in taste, in opinions, in morals, and in intellect. To that class

we may leave it to refine the vernacular dialects of the country, to enrich those dialects with terms of science borrowed from the Western nomenclature, and to render them by degrees fit vehicles for conveying knowledge to the great mass of the population". A few years later introduction of English in 1837 for official use in place of Persian (during the period of William Bentinck) had quickened the process leading to the decline of Muslim domination in social and political realm of 19th century Bengal.

Here, the case of Hindu attitude to modern education through English, and their appointments by the colonial government needs a few highlights synoptically viewing of their advancements under colonialism. It is found that the powerful and rich Hindus had built up good rapport with the Muslim rulers since the time of Alibardi Khan. Under the British Raj too, they made steady advancements by learning English quickly and also by taking up the opportunities of English education. It seems that instead of being apathetic to Western education Hindu attitude was responsive to what the British Raj wanted to set up, whereas the persistence of Islamic antipathy to the West had an adverse effect on the extent of Muslim's response to the emerging culture which continued to grow on an English-Bengali synthesis throughout the 19th century in Bengal. It played a major role for the decadence of the Muslims and coagulation of their socio-cultural insularity.

It might be critiqued that there was, in fact, no connection between the annulment of Persian and decline of the Muslim elites. But it seems that disappearance of Persian stripped them of the important means of coercive power and domination, which was significant in the context of political developments of that time. Their elevation to the position of ruling class and reversal at the hands of the British power had caused their gradual retrogression. Yet there is ample scope to suggest that not the social and political dislocation were alone responsible for

their decline. The process was precipitated by their prolonged antipathy to English education which drove them heavily towards the orthodox interpretations of the scriptures and Islam-based responses to alien culture, patterns of behavior and action.

The Ashraf-Atraf Dichotomy

Consolidation of community-bond hinges on an unwavering faith in inexorable belief, values and principles, based on religious scriptures and practice of common rituals. Muslims are generally held as a homogeneous community because faith binds them all. So, local or regional variations are not the matters of great significance in constructing Islamic identity and those variations are not held as obstacles to taking 'faith' to their bosoms. Yet, social disparities and dichotomy, despite the pervasive influence of 'faith', reflect disunity among the Muslims which is important for a symptomatic understanding of the Muslim worldview in colonial Bengal.

Opposed to the common view that they belong to a homogeneous community, as Rafiuddin Ahmed (1996) suggests that the Muslims in colonial Bengal were divided into two mutually exclusive groups: Ashrafs and the Atrafs. Ashrafs were mainly Urdu-speaking elites of central Asian origin, while their ordinary Bengali-speaking counterparts were known as Atrafs. The Atrafs inhabited the large part of the Bengal districts who formed the majority. But the upper class Muslim Ashrafs were reluctant to accept them as real Muslims. To them Atrafs were only wine-vendors, weavers, etc. This Ashraf-Atraf dichotomy, based on the claim of central Asian origin had laid the basis for social disunity among the Muslims. The dichotomy between the original and the converted Muslims had spread its tentacles over the whole region, and that gave rise to two linguistically divided groups, yet bound by common faith. (Ahmed, 1996)

Despite this unity, based on common faith, nothing could prevent concentration of wealth and education in the Ashraf society. The 1901 census shows that the Urdu-speaking urban elite Mughal Muslims and Syeds had topped the table in education. The Ashrafs of higher origin did not have any contact even with the Bengali-speaking lower Ashrafs. The case of Syed Amir Ali is in point. He lived in Calcutta but had no connection or concern for the problems of the ordinary Bengali Muslims (Ahmed, 1996, p. 14). We also see that the bulk of Muslim population belonged to the non-Ashraf categories consisting of sheikh (cultivator), nikari (fisherman), kalu (oil-presser), hajam (barber), jolaha (weaver), etc. They had no scope of education and employment in colonial administration.

In this perspective Ahmed notes that the basic structural weakness that had retarded the growth of any understanding between the elite Muslims and their rural masses was the absence of a responsible intermediary group willing to play a positive role as a link between the two. It is argued that a sharp dichotomy between the Ashrafs and Atrafs had handicapped the Muslims. But the Hindu society did not suffer from this kind of disability because of the rapid growth of the powerful middle class as the bulwark of its advancements, and they were certainly drawn from higher social castes, like the Brahmins, Kayasthas and Baidyas. So, the presence of an intermediary or middle class in colonial Bengal among the Hindus acted as the harbinger of social change, while its absence among the Muslims had hindered their advancement, and sustained the dichotomy between these linguistic groups of the Muslim community. In this context it is relevant to note that the Census of 1872 revealed that nearly 48 per cent of the total population of Bengal at that time was Muslim, the majority of who lived in the marshy, low-lying tracts of eastern Bengal, and in some districts their size varied between 60 per cent and 70 per cent.

In the backdrop of inter-community disparities it is worthwhile to highlight the pattern of distribution of the Hindus and Muslims in various occupations and professions. This explains the reasons that hindered the growth of an intermediary class among the Muslims. While the Muslims predominantly belonged to the cultivating classes; the high-caste Hindus dominated the land-holding, professional and mercantile occupations. By the time the British had come, the upper caste Hindus had already surpassed even the Ashrafs in the field of educational advancements. Moreover, more than 90 per cent of the non-elite, ordinary Muslims belonged to agricultural and low-service groups, and many of them were actually tillers of the soil (Ahmed, 1996, p. 2). Thus, although they were big enough in size, power and status in society by and large had rested with the upper caste Hindus. Most of the opportunities were appropriated by the Hindus, while in the absence of an intermediary class the Muslims had stagnated in the countryside without education and employment. Obviously, we need to analyze the life-world of the vast majority of non-Ashraf Muslim women of colonial Bengal in the light of their subalternity, a fact which was rooted in their social and gender-based marginalization, first as Muslim and then as women.

Urdu-Bengali Contradiction: a Dilemma

Mediation of language is a *sin qua non* for forging links between widely separated social groups. It is found that after the decline of Persian, Urdu had gradually gained ground as the language of the Indian Muslim elite. Persian was made to perish as the language of colonial administration. But before that the language had started to decline after the break in diplomatic relations between the Mughal emperor Aurangzeb and the Safavid Persia. Also, in early 18th century, Muslim elite of Delhi had begun to discard Persian in favour of Urdu. But the problem arose from the absence of Indian milieu in early Urdu writings that had caused the

rejection of the language by the bulk of the Hindu community (Ahmad, 1964, pp. 251-5). So, neither Persian nor Urdu did emerge as the common language of both the Hindus and Muslims.

However, in 19th century Bengal we get a different situation. Despite Bengali was the main provincial language of both the Hindus and the Muslims the socio-political milieu was not conducive to the birth of a cohesive 'speech community', comprising all the communities and linguistic groups. We find that apart from Bengali Hindu's alienation from Urdu, the age-old dichotomy between the Ashrafs and Atrafs, based on status and language had also created a dilemma within the Muslim society. As for the elite Ashraf Muslims there was a preference for Urdu instead of Bengali as the medium of learning. Also, there was an enormous focus on Arabic and religious teachings. This is revealed in the fact that Rokeya Shakhawat Hossain lamented that she could not introduce Bengali in her Sakhawat Memorial School as a natural choice, and had to wait for a long 16 years to start a course in Bengali after its inception.

If we look at the situation in 19th century Bengal we would find that Bengali was the most popular language and also the *lingua franca* among Bengali Hindus and Bengali Muslims. Yet, the Bengal Muslims were ambivalent on the issue of language because Urdu was given pre-eminence to strengthen their own cultural identity. Rafiuddin Ahmed (1996) thinks that the linguistic divide had a cascading effect. This cultural ambivalence of the Bengali Muslims found its characteristic expression in their attitude towards their mother-tongue Bengali (Ahmed, 1996, p. 119). So, the divisive issues between the Hindus and the Muslims which had encumbered the social and political life of 19th century Bengal had brought the language question to the forefront.

The dilemma centred around the question whether Bengali was compatible with

their religious aspirations. Increasing Sanskritization of Bengali through the efforts of the Fort William College and Hinduization of contents had caused their alienation and inclination to Urdu as the language of the community. But at the same time it was also true that full-scale replacement of Bengali by Urdu was not possible. Hence, the dilemma persisted to the detriment of educational and cultural advancements of the Muslims. The entire community was in a dilemma due to this unsettled issue. We cannot insulate the lifeworld of those women from these hindrances since they were almost in a state of atrophy in the absence of educational opportunities and gender equity. The issue was unsettled and their ambivalence on 'language question' had beleaguered their advancements in education. Language dilemma in conjunction with gender inequality was instrumental in fixing their place within the enclosure of 'home'. Clearly, the circumstances were not propitious for their advancement. Perhaps due to these circumstances we do not notice any substantial progress in Muslim women's education and their coming to the public domain.

Hindu-Muslim Relation and Nationalism

We know that the Hindus and the Muslims have a long experience of uneasy relationship, the history of which needs a separate discussion. Arrival of colonialism had created an opportunity for the Hindu intelligentsia for altering the balance in their favour. Inception of English education and the fetish for Anglicization, and the growth of English-knowing urbanized Bhadrakalok society from among the upper caste Hindus had put them in a far better position than the Muslims.

Moreover the developments, revealed through Hindu-Muslim divide on the issue of Partition of Bengal and Muslim attitude towards the

Swadeshi and Hinduised version of nationalism reflected through the use of Hindu symbols like Rakhibandhan, and worship of Goddess Kali for Shakti Aradhana and the 'nation' as mother had deepened the differences between these two communities. Further, the British policy of 'divide and rule' and granting of 'communal award' and 'separate electorate' in 1932 provided an adequate stimulus to their alienation from each other. It is important to note here that due to Hindu religious flavour in the Swadeshi movement, a large section of the Muslims opposed the movement for the interest of their community. Naturally Muslim women had hardly any role in this movement (Hossain, 2003, p. 216).

Life -World of Muslim Women

What is important in this context is the need to address the 'women question' in the backdrop of mainstream 'nationalist' movement and Muslim society's pre-occupation with community-solidarity for the assertion of their political weight in which the question of gender equity was preposterous. It appears that both had put the 'question' of women's position on hold for greater interests. Women's participation in nationalist or in identity politics, both Hindu and Muslim, was not at all an issue of great importance at that time. Indifference to women's issues was premised on the nationalist idea that 'women question' could be put to rest for the greater cause of national liberation. They can wait till the nation is free from the bondage of foreign rule. In the case of the Muslims the immediate need was to act for guarding community's interest. Side by side, Indian National Congress too, had lost its appeal to the Muslims. And the birth of Muslim League (1906) registered the formal breach and validated the distrust between the Hindus and the Muslims.

Thus, it seems that the movement towards modernization of Muslim women was stunted by the structural constraints,

ramifications of contemporary politics and the ruptures within the society. All those developments made them captive to the situational constraints that prevailed in 19th century Bengal. We may sum up that their lifeworld was afflicted with insularity, alienation, backwardness in education and employments. Their lifeworld was tethered to the structural constraints, and in consequence of all those developments andarmahal, i.e. the enclosure of home and family became important site for attention, instead of outer domain, the domain of formal-institutional education, participation and women's presence in the public sphere. In explaining the relation between the 'nation and women', Partha Chatterjee (1993) refers to the separation of social space into home and the world, based on material-spiritual dichotomy. Home belongs to the inner domain of sovereignty which has its own conception of women and gender relations. This had to remain unaffected by the treacherous terrain of the material world. No encroachment from outside would be allowed in that inner sanctum. Muslim women's life-world seems to have been shaped by this rigid dichotomy between the 'home' and the 'world'. (Chatterjee, 1997)

Thus, the plight of Bengali Muslim women has to be understood in the backdrop of the declining position of the Muslims as a community in Bengal which was in discordance with 19th century's socio-political generation. Degeneration of the community is reflected in Christian Missionary Rev. James Long's caution made in 1869: 'The Muslims of Bengal have degenerated, are degenerating and will sink to a still lower depth unless steps are taken to remedy what must be an evil attended with serious consequences'.

Looking Inward: Constructing the Domestic Ideology for Muslim Women

The context of Muslim women comes in the backdrop of the trinity of colonialism, nationalism and community's outlook which connects the inner sanctum of family and home, idealized on the pedestal of Islamic principles during the 19th century. The issue obviously urges to make an account of the inner domain of Muslim women. The conception of andarmahal, i.e. the inner sanctum was already defined according to tradition. Their life-world was thoroughly guided by the Islamic norms where patriarchy reigned supreme. Islamic laws and tradition were frequently cited to account for gender relations. The home, the private, the personal--- becomes the ideal site for maintaining tradition and Islamic values. So, before taking up the issue of molecular changes we need to explain the pigeonhole of 'family', which was at the nerve-centre of private sphere around which their lifeworld had revolved.

A few references would show that the dichotomy between private and public sphere in Muslim family was expressed through the division of residence into the inner part and outer part. Shaista Ikramullah in 'Behind the Veil' (1953) narrated the division of space in the traditional families, and male entry without close blood relation was forbidden. In Aborodhbasini Rokeya Shakhawat Hossain narrated her life in seclusion. She told that 'from the age 5 we girls had to observe purdah. Men are not allowed to enter the antahpur'. Rokeya, Fatima, Sufia Kamal, etc., stated that they spent childhood mostly inside the andarmahal, playing idols, listening stories from grandmothers, learning and reading religious texts, taught to help household chores in cooking, sewing, knitting, etc. From an early age their lifeworld was castled within the circles of home and family. They were brought up with the idea of their future role as wife and mother in mind. Islamic laws were religiously followed. Thus, the domestic ideology was constructed in tune with tradition.

Private life and the Dynamics of Change

We have already argued on the complex issue of Hindu-Muslim relation as an important index, but have not so far focused on exploring the undercurrents of change in their lives under the impact of uppercaste Hindu women's elevation to dignity in family and society. Recent studies suggest (S. N. Amin: 1996) that Muslim women's changing notion of home, family, women's education and anti-colonial struggle was almost synchronous with the change in the consciousness and life-worlds of Hindu Women, spurred by the reform movements in spite of nationalism's refusal to address the women question. So, it is a serious point to know whether the arrival of a new conception about social, political, home and the issues, connected with their private lives had changed under the impact of the changing lifeworlds of Hindu women.

It is found that in spite of the significance of tradition the lifeworlds of Muslim women had begun to change under the impact of Brahmo reforms and English-education. It is found that a new professional bhadralok social class had gradually come up which was opposed to the previous conception of 'avijat' and 'grihastha'. It is also found (S. N. Amin: *ibid*) that late 19th and early 20th century Brahmo reform movement had a discernable impact on the Muslim psyche. O'Mally considered that the three higher Hindu castes and Muhammadans of birth, breeding and education were bhadraloks. Yet, there were resistances and disapproval from within the community and a general approval for the name 'Mian-Saheb and Begum, etc. Hence, the nomenclature 'bhadralok' was unresolved and universal acceptance of Muslim

bhadramahila as a social category was a problem³.

However, Amin argues that the emergence of Muslim gentle-women or Muslim Bhadramahila in Bengal is to be viewed in the context of Bengal Muslim identity. The bhadralok-bhadramahila appellation was a new phenomenon in colonial Bengal from which the Muslims were not entirely isolated. We have to borrow from Meredith Borthwick's 'Changing Role of Women in Bengal' (1849-1905, p. 54) in which she argues that by the end of the 19th century an articulate group of women, able to make their voices heard through public institutional channels, had appeared. They came to be known as bhadramahila, used to describe the female members of the bhadralok families. The model was created by the Brahmo reformers. They were consciously welded into a body with a progressive image and seen as the pioneers of a new way of life to be adopted by non-Brahmin women.

So, in spite of the prevalence of tenacious tradition, we cannot ignore that there

³ See Amin Sonia Nishat (1996): *The World of Muslim Women in Colonial Bengal: 1896-1939*, Leiden: E.J. Brill.

Amin Sonia Nishat (2001): 'The Changing World of Bengali Muslim Women: the Dream and Efforts of Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain' in R. Ahmed ed. *Understanding the Bengal Muslims: Interpretative Essays*, Oxford University Press, New Delhi.

was a transition; however, restricted within its limits. Not strident, but an undercurrent of change was felt in gender relations, domination of patriarchy, attitude to religion and community. Although they could not wrench women's substantive freedom from the control of patriarchy their own experience and perception of home, family and community and anxiety for women's backwardness urged them to act for change --- take the pen and working for the upliftment of Muslim women. Their foremost emphasis was on the spread of Muslim Girls' education and removal of illiteracy and reconstruction of private life in terms of dignity even against the perceived backlash of patriarchy and religious orthodoxy.

At this point we need to refer to the rare moment when a powerful cultural and economic group was born. There was a new cultural articulation of the Bengal Ashraf (who descended economically) to meet the upwardly mobile *ajlaf* or *atraf* class to constitute the 'bhadra sampraday'. The cultural idiom, based on urban syncretism which may be called Bengalicization, began to express itself through Bengali.

It therefore, seems that the forces of change were conspicuous among the Bengali Muslims and their women, so far as the conditions in 19th century Bengal is concerned. The sphere of 'family' was in the process of being re-defined and reformed through the rise of a new ideology, when Bengal Renaissance touched this community during the closing years of the 19th century.

Amin notes that since the early 20th century Muslim women had begun to express their moderate views on marriage, divorce, polygamy, age of marriage, *purdah*, educational backwardness, etc. This continued in the later decades of the 20th century in varying degrees. A change was visible, led by a section of women which was small but powerful. Emergence of feminist consciousness from Taherunnesa(1860s)

to Sufia Kamal (1911) fostered a change in the worldview of Muslim women. Apart from them the women like Latifunnesa (1877, Bamabodhini), Faizunnesa (1873, Rupzalat), Khairunnesa (1870-1912, Amader Sikshar Antaray, in Nabanur, 1904) and above all Rokeya S. Hossain (1880-1932, Abarodhbasini, Stree Jatir Abanati, 1905, Narir Adhikar 1932, Ardhangi 1905, Alankar na Badge of Slavery --- are the glaring testimonies of their emancipatory writings, which expounded a human philosophy of women's awakening. Of them Rokeya Begum stands out as a woman extraordinaire who pioneered Muslim women's new worldview of emancipation.

Thus, there was a transition of Muslim women from *bibi* and *begum* to *Bhadramahila* due to the rise of a new professional and enlightened class. Assertion of Bengali-speaking Muslims, moving away from the hitherto influential North-Indian Ashrafs elevated their new thinking about domestic life that made them responsive to a deep-going social change all over the Bengali society. In many of her writings and addresses Rokeya hailed the Muslim men as 'bhadra' while women as *bhadramahila*. (Baby show 1920, Shishu Palan, 1327, BS). This was the moment that spilled over from the 19th century to the early decades of the 20th century which can be marked as the period from when the identity of the Muslims as Bengali-middle class was formed. It was from this class that their daughters, wives and sisters went to school and stepped outside the *andarmahal* which beckoned a change.

References

Ahmad, A. (1964). *Studies in Islamic Culture in the Indian Environment*. New Delhi.: Oxford University Press,.

Ahmed, R. (1996). *The Bengal Muslims, 1871-1906: A Quest for Identity*. New Delhi.: Oxford University Press,.

Chatterjee, P. (1997). *The Nation and Its Fragments*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Hossain, A. (2003). *Muslim Women's Struggle for Freedom in Colonial Bengal (1873-1940)*. Kolkata.: Progressive Publishers.

Panikkar, K. (1986). The Intellectual History of colonial India. In S. R. Thapar, *Situating Intellectual History for Sarvepalli Gopal* . New Delhi: Oxford University Press.